

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
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***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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OPTIMIZING RADIOLOGICAL PATHWAYS FOR EARLY DETECTION OF OSTEOGENIC SARCOMA IN CHILDREN**Yusupalieva G.A., Shakirova L.M.**

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Resume. The multimodal approach to radiological diagnostics of osteogenic sarcoma in children integrates consecutive use of conventional radiography, radionuclide imaging, and computed tomography to ensure early detection and accurate assessment of tumour spread. This diagnostic sequence enhances sensitivity in identifying both primary bone lesions and clinically silent metastases, allowing for timely differentiation from benign conditions and inflammatory processes. The combined use of these complementary imaging modalities improves diagnostic precision, supports effective treatment planning, and contributes to better clinical outcomes in pediatric patients with suspected or confirmed osteogenic sarcoma.

Keywords: radiological diagnostics, osteogenic sarcoma, children, radiography, radionuclide imaging, computed tomography

**БОЛАЛАРДА ОСТЕОГЕН САРКОМАНИ ЭРТА АНИҚЛАШНИНГ РАДИОЛОГИК
УСУЛЛАРИНИ ОПТИМАЛЛАШТИРИШ****Юсупалиева Г.А., Шакирова Л.М.**

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Резюме. Болаларда остеоген саркоманинг рентгенологик диагностикасига мултимодал ёндашув ўсма тарқалишини эрта аниқлаш ва аниқ баҳолашни таъминлаш учун анъанавий рентгенография, радионуклид визуализация ва компьютер томографиясидан изчил фойдаланишни ўз ичига олади. Диагностиканинг бундай кетма-кетлиги суякларнинг бирламчи шикастланишларини ҳам, клиник жиҳатдан намойён бўлмаган метастазларни ҳам аниқлашда сезгирликни оширади, уларни ўз вақтида хавфсиз ҳолатлар ва яллигланиш жараёнларидан ажратиш имконини беради. Ушбу қўшимча визуализация усулларини биргаликда қўллаш диагностика аниқлигини оширади, даволашни самарали режалаштиришига ёрдам беради ва остеоген саркомага шубҳа қилинган ёки тасдиқланган таиҳиси бўлган педиатрик беморларда клиник натижаларни яхшилашга ёрдам беради.

Калит сўзлар: рентгенологик диагностика, остеоген саркома, болалар, рентгенография, радионуклид визуализация, компьютер томография.

**ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ЛУЧЕВЫХ МЕТОДОВ ДЛЯ РАННЕГО ВЫЯВЛЕНИЯ ОСТЕОГЕННОЙ
САРКОМЫ У ДЕТЕЙ****Юсупалиева Г.А., Шакирова Л.М.**

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Резюме. Мультимодальный подход к рентгенологической диагностике остеогенной саркомы у детей включает последовательное использование традиционной рентгенографии, радионуклидной визуализации и компьютерной томографии для обеспечения раннего выявления и точной оценки распространения опухоли. Такая последовательность диагностики повышает чувствительность при выявлении как первичных поражений костей, так и клинически не проявляющихся метастазов, позволяя своевременно отличить их от доброкачественных состояний и воспалительных процессов. Комбинированное использование этих дополнительных методов визуализации повышает точность диагностики, способствует эффективному планированию лечения и способствует улучшению клинических результатов у педиатрических пациентов с подозрением на остеогенную саркому или подтвержденным диагнозом.

Ключевые слова: рентгенологическая диагностика, остеогенная саркома, дети, рентгенография, радионуклидная визуализация, компьютерная томография

Relevance. Classical osteosarcoma is the most frequent primary sarcoma of high-grade malignancy with bone lesions. Despite this, it accounts for less than 1% of all malignant tumours occurring in the US population. The incidence ranges from 10 to 26 new cases per 1 million global population per year. It has a bimodal age distribution. First peak in the 10-14 year age group and second peak over 40 years of age. It is

extremely rare in children under 5 years of age. The gender distribution favours the male population with a ratio of 1.35.[2,7]

In localised osteosarcoma, when the tumour has not spread, the prognosis is favourable and the survival rate is about 60-70%. However, in metastatic osteosarcoma, when the tumour has spread to other organs, the survival rate is reduced to 20-30% [3].

Early diagnosis and timely treatment of osteosarcoma, when the tumour is confined to the bone, greatly increases the chances of recovery. Metastatic osteosarcoma has a significantly worse prognosis, as metastases can spread to the lungs, other bones and other organs [1].

Thus, untimely and erroneous diagnosis leads to a worse prognosis of the course of the disease. The analysis of diagnostic errors made in the diagnosis of this pathology was carried out on the basis of domestic and foreign literature and on the basis of retrospective study of radiographs of patients with osteogenic sarcoma taking into account morphological examination data. The percentage of misdiagnoses, according to literature data, averages 15 to 20%. Only the complex of applied radiation methods taking into account clinical symptoms and morphological examination data will make it possible to bring the reliability of osteogenic sarcoma diagnosis as close as possible to the true one, leading to timely and adequate treatment [4,5,6].

The aim of the present work was to evaluate a system of multimodal early radial diagnostics in the detection of osteogenic sarcoma in children.

Research results. The study and analysis of diagnostic errors identified during the initial examination of patients with osteogenic sarcoma have shown that these inaccuracies arise from several interrelated factors. The primary cause is the absence of specific clinical and radiological manifestations in the early stages of tumour development, which objectively complicates differential diagnosis. Diagnostic difficulties are aggravated by an insufficiently thorough assessment of anamnestic data, particularly in cases where trauma provokes increasing pain and swelling in the affected area. A significant contribution is made by the low level of oncological vigilance among general practitioners, some of whom prescribe warming or physiotherapeutic procedures without prior radiological evaluation. Errors also stem from the limited qualifications of primary-care radiologists, whose examinations often remain incomplete and whose knowledge of both early and characteristic radiological signs of bone sarcoma is inadequate. The insufficient study and recognition of initial radiological manifestations of osteogenic sarcoma further hinder timely diagnosis. Additionally, low oncological awareness among the population leads to delayed medical consultations. Finally, the incomplete and insufficient use of available diagnostic modalities—particularly radionuclide techniques and mandatory morphological verification—during primary patient assessment contributes to a high proportion of diagnostic errors in this category of cases. According to the authors' data, the retrospective analysis of errors made in clinics on the first radiographs showed that even in specialised diagnostic departments of oncological clinics incorrect interpretation of radiographs made up to 17%. In the overwhelming majority of cases, up to 82% of erroneous conclusions, these errors concerned distinctive recognition within a group of malignant tumours. In this connection we consider that only the complex of applied radial methods taking into account clinical symptomatology and morphological examination data will allow to bring the reliability of diagnostics of osteogenic sarcoma as close as possible to the true one leading to timely and adequate treatment.

Based on the above, it is established that in the early recognition of osteosarcoma it is necessary to take into account the following:

-The radiological symptom-complex of the initial manifestations of osteogenic sarcoma is an area of tumour bone formation, a focus of destruction or their combinations without destruction of the outer contour of the cortical standing and periostosis, as well as the absence of signs of reparation and reaction of bone tissue surrounding the sarcomatous focus.

-The clinical and radiological picture of osteogenic sarcoma and the dynamics of process development do not depend on such factors as tumour localisation in the skeleton, sex and age of patients.

For timely diagnosis and adequate treatment it is reasonable to distinguish periosteal and intracortical osteosarcomas in the radiological classification of osteogenic sarcoma, in addition to the generally accepted varieties (osteoblastic, osteolytic and mixed). Periosteal osteosarcoma, unlike other varieties, is manifested in the radiological image only by the presence of periosteal layering, from radial spicules, fringed periostosis to rough non-homogeneous overlays without visible lesions of other bone layers. Intracortical osteosarcoma is a diaphyseal tumour initially localised in the thickened cortical layer in the form of small focal destruction without the periosteal reaction characteristic of inflammatory processes. The possible combination of the simultaneous development of osteogenic sarcoma and a variant of tibial tuberosity formation in adolescents requires increased oncological vigilance.

Bone metastases may occur before the appearance of lung metastases, which necessitates radionuclide examination of the skeleton in all observations. Scintigraphy can clarify the boundaries of the extraosseous

component of the tumour and detect distant metastases in the skeleton. Computed tomography significantly facilitates diagnosis in complex anatomical areas and assessment of local tumour spread.

The **analysis of the causes of diagnostic errors** at different stages of examination of patients with osteogenic sarcoma has shown: - at the initial examination the frequency of errors is associated with low qualification of doctors, insufficient oncological alertness of both doctors and patients, lack of clinical and radiological criteria for early diagnosis; -the absence of pathognomonic clinical and radiological signs of osteogenic sarcoma make differential diagnosis within the group of malignant neoplasms extremely difficult, being the main reason for erroneous diagnoses in specialised oncological institutions.

The development and improvement of sequential radiation-based diagnostic methods has created a solid foundation for a comprehensive approach to the detection of osteogenic sarcoma. This approach requires mandatory radiological examination of all patients presenting with bone and joint pain—especially children and adolescents—ensuring that, in cases associated with trauma, radiographs are performed no later than two weeks after the initial medical visit. When even minimal clinical or radiological signs raise suspicion of bone sarcoma, it is essential to refer such children immediately from their place of residence to specialised clinics where morphological verification, qualified diagnostics and adequate treatment are available. The identified variants of tibial tuberosity development should also be carefully evaluated due to the possible simultaneous emergence of osteogenic sarcoma in this area. Radiological assessment should include not only the suspected bone segment but also adjacent joints, since clinically silent metastases, often localised in the epimetaphyseal regions of long bones, may be detected. Children diagnosed with inflammatory processes, benign tumours or tumour-like bone lesions require dynamic monitoring, especially when treatment proves ineffective. During annual medical examinations, it is important to identify and stratify risk groups among children and adolescents for targeted clinical and radiological surveillance. Upon admission to specialised oncology centres, all patients with osteogenic sarcoma must undergo radionuclide scanning of the entire skeleton to detect metastases, as skeletal dissemination may precede the appearance of pulmonary metastases. Computed tomography should be used only after standard radiography to determine the local extent of tumour involvement. Since no diagnostic modality provides absolutely specific features for osteogenic sarcoma or eliminates the risk of misdiagnosis, mandatory morphological verification remains indispensable in every case.

Conclusion. For the examination of children with osteogenic sarcoma or suspected osteogenic sarcoma, it is recommended to use the developed and improved multimodal sequence of radiological methods, which includes separate radiological techniques in a specific order: conventional radiography, radionuclide examination, and X-ray computed tomography when indicated. This structured diagnostic approach ensures maximum sensitivity in detecting early tumour changes and allows for timely identification of both local and distant metastatic lesions. The consistent use of these modalities significantly enhances diagnostic accuracy and reduces the likelihood of errors at the initial stages of patient evaluation. Such an integrated strategy ultimately contributes to earlier initiation of appropriate treatment and improves the overall prognosis for affected children.

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